

Ifugao

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions

The Ifugao inhabit the western mountain ranges of northern Luzon, which is an island of the Philippines. The Ifugao are agriculturalists and use extensive rice terraces with irrigation. Settlements consist of autonomous districts, each containing several hamlets; neither chiefs nor councils are present. Although the Ifugao have had contact with Christian missionaries, the remoteness of Ifugao settlements and elaborate traditional religious beliefs have prevented substantial Christian influence. The Ifugao religion consists of, "a mixture of exceedingly complex polytheism, ancestor worship, and a mythology that is used as an instrument of magic" (Barton, 1919:10). Anyone may study to become a priest; consequently, almost every adult man is one. Because the Ifugao do not have official political leadership, and religion is tied up with the function of almost all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. This entry focuses around the time of 1910.

Date Range: 1890 CE - 1920 CE

Region: Northern Luzon, Philippines

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Philippines

The Kiangnan group located in the northern third of Luzon Island, Philippines, circa 1910

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oa19-000>
- Source 1 Description: Malone, M. J., & Skoggard, I. A. (1999). *Culture Summary: Ifugao*. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oa19-001>

– Source 1 Description: Barton, R. F. (1946). Religion Of The Ifugao. Memoir. Menasha, Wis.: American Anthropological Association.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oa19-012>

– Source 2 Description: Barton, R. F. (1930). Half-Way Sun: Life Among The Headhunters Of The Philippines. New York: Brewer & Warren, Inc.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oa19-002>

– Source 3 Description: Barton, R. F. (1919). Ifugao Law. Publications In American Archaeology And Ethnology. Berkeley: University of California Press.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "True, garrisons and missions had been established in a few localities among them; but owing to the scattered character of the population, the independent spirit of the people, their natural conservatism, and the lack of tact and consideration on the part of the Spanish officials and missionaries, practically no progress had been made in christianizing or civilizing them...This geographic isolation has tended to keep the Ifugao culture relatively pure and uninfluenced by contact with the outside world. Two or three military posts were fitfully maintained in Ifugao by the Spaniards during the last half century of their sovereignty; but the lives of the natives were little affected thereby" (Barton, 1919:8).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), internal warfare seems to occur constantly any time of the year (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), external warfare seems to occur constantly any time of the year (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is not a process for assigning religious affiliation other than being born into the group.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is not active recruitment for new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, indicates that there is considerable overlap between political and religious leaders (Ross, 1983; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, indicates that there is considerable overlap between political and religious leaders (Ross, 1983; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing: there is, consequently, no written law. They have no form of political government: there is, therefore, no constitutional or statutory law. Inasmuch as they have no courts or judges, there is no law based on judicial decisions. Ifugao law has two sources of origin: taboo (which is essentially religious) and custom. The customary law is the more important from the greater frequency of its application" (Barton, 1919:11).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is not a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 130000

Notes: "The Ifugaos are the largest pagan tribe under our flag. Numbering 130,000, they rank seventh in population among the peoples of the Philippines" (Barton, 1930:60).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In my part of Ifugaoland, any man of normal mentality may and ought to become a priest. The higher his rank and qualities, the better priest he makes. A poor man officiates only within his own

family unless his personality and the vigor of his invocations gain him repute. When called outside his family, the priest receives five or ten cents for his services, as well as all the meat and rice wine he can consume. Women of the upper and middle classes usually become priestesses, but do not officiate except in agricultural ceremonies and the 'women's' ceremony" (Barton, 1930:142).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: "Ifugao priests are men who take their positions voluntarily and after a period of apprenticeship" (Malone and Skoggard, 1999).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6; note, identical to SCCS Variable 66).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6; note, identical to SCCS Variable 66).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "There are conflicting beliefs about the time when the soul leaves the body. According to one view it is called away by Imbagaiyan (the Conductor of Souls, p. 86), before death. When an ancestor or a deity wants the soul of a living person, he calls Imbagaiyan and sends him to bring it...According to another view, the soul escapes from the body at the moment of death, not from an orifice but through the solid flesh, usually through the top of the head. But if the legs or arms twitch a great deal, it is thought that the soul is escaping through them" (Barton, 1946:170-171).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "It is said that it [the soul] can sometimes be seen in the form of a thin haze or smoke" (Barton, 1946:171).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: During the entombment rites, a priest remains in the house where the corpse sat in the death chair prior to entombment. The priest coaxes the soul to "see a group of folk—in the spirit world, of course—going to a prestige feast that is being given over the ridge in the adjacent valley. He has the soul go back into its former house, put on its best garb and go along with this group. Arrived at the prestige feast, the soul enjoys itself hugely, gets drunk and does not come back. On the morrow, the folk of this valley persuade the soul to come along with them to another prestige feast in another valley a little further away. There it also enjoys itself and gets too drunk to return home. The tulud continues on and on—stage by stage the soul is beguiled farther and farther away. The Conductors of Souls, from their place in the Skyworld, see it and come down and take charge of it, bespeaking for it courteous and deferential treatment and coaxing it to prestige feasts at still greater distances. It finally loses all thought of returning home and is delivered to its kindred in Kadungayan, the Region of the Dead, where it stays, and, according to the priest's tulud, never comes back" (Barton, 1946:180).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Barton, 1946:180

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...Kadungayan, the Region of the Dead..." (Barton, 1946:180). See previous questions describing the journey of the soul further and further beyond this world.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on the treatment of corpses.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Arrived at the sepulchre, the limbs are drawn tight to the body and tied to a squatting position; the corpse is then wrapped in shrouds, rarely fewer than two being used and many more if the deceased were rich. The corpse is then drawn into the sepulchre by two men and placed in a sitting position (or, in some regions, laid on its side) at the farther wall, on a sort of earthen shelf raised from the floor" (Barton, 1946:179).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "Arrived at the sepulchre, the limbs are drawn tight to the body and tied to a squatting position; the corpse is then wrapped in shrouds, rarely fewer than two being used and many more if the deceased were rich. The corpse is then drawn into the sepulchre by two men and placed in a sitting position (or, in some regions, laid on its side) at the farther wall, on a sort of earthen shelf raised from the floor" (Barton, 1946:179).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "Sometimes secondary burials take place three to five years later, especially if the deceased is unhappy and causing illness among the living" (Malone and Skoggard, 1999).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: After washing and dressing the body of the deceased, the body is tied to a specially made death chair. The body may be moved two or three times during the course of the funerary ceremonies. (see Barton, 1946:172-178).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "If the deceased were well-to-do, there are two or three offerings of animals to the soul; if poor, only one" (Barton, 1946:176).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Barton, 1946:176

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a poor person is entombed on the third day after death, that of a middle-class person on the fifth day, and that of a wealthy person on the seventh to the thirteenth day. The wealthy person's corpse may be moved, as has been said, two or three times" (Barton, 1946:178). For a full description of Ifugao burial practices, see Barton, 1946:178-180.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: "The most widespread and generally used form is the lubok, a sepulchre dug into a bank of soft stone...In some regions male and female kindred are interred in the same tomb; in others the kinship avoidances operate even after death to make this seem indecent. Kindred are always interred together, but neither parents' lineage predominates: that is to say that whether a man be interred in a sepulchre of the kindred on the mother's side or on the father's depends usually on which sepulchre be most conveniently at hand" (Barton, 1946:196).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The five regions of the Ifugao cosmology are inhabited by an enormous number of deities. Ifugao god-creation has proceeded on an almost unlimited scale. There is little of importance that the Ifugao knows about, under his sun or under his earth or at the corners of his earth, that he has not deified. Yet he has no creator or story of creation, and he has no supreme deity" (Barton, 1946:11).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: "No god is believed to have been the creator and no god is supreme" (Barton, 1930:122).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Whenever there is a death the soul of the deceased roams about for a while as a temporary or transient ghost. Ghosts of those dead from natural causes are not much feared, but those dead from violence or childbirth are" (Barton, 1946:87). "The Banig are permanent ghosts—distinguished from transient ones" (Barton, 1930:139). Previously human spirits are not described in great detail, making it difficult to determine specific aspects of their character.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: There is an extensive list of deities among the Ifugao, including those associated with, for example, agriculture, reproduction, social relations, and elements of nature. See questions below for more information.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

Notes: "The strongest of all Ifugao taboos is that against eating the food, drinking the water or wine or chewing the betels of an enemy kinship group. It is a powerful deterrent from making peace, for infraction of the taboo entails punishment by a sub-group of the hidit deities with particularly stubborn ailments which no ordinary sickness rites will ameliorate" (Barton, 1946:52).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Agricultural Gods are very largely the personifications of natural forces. They have a special attractiveness to the Ifugaos because of their ability miraculously to increase the rice while the crop is being harvested and soon after it has been stored in the granary. They make the grains swell large in cooking, and can bring it about that 'when the women take rice from the store, the place left vacant shall be filled again'" (Barton, 1930:123).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "The deities are not regarded as tyrants except sometimes in the case of granary idols with their inordinate appetites for blood and rice cakes and their spitefulness if their appetites be left unsatisfied" (Barton, 1946:207).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Cause illness/disease

Notes: "All deities are believed to be capable of afflicting men with disease and are believed occasionally to do so" (Barton, 1946:62).

– Yes [specify]: Protect from spirits that cause sickness

Notes: The Maki-Ubaiya class of deities is invoked for protection from spirits that cause sickness (see Barton, 1946:16).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The Ifugao conceives of his deities as specialized, as being of various degrees of importance in ritual, sacrifice and in the attention due them, and he conceives of them as being grouped in more than forty classes (I keep finding new ones)" (Barton, 1946:12).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: "But to some degree the classes overlap; a few of the hero-ancestors, tutelary and more powerful deities belong to six or more classes. The Ifugao classification is almost as slipshod and inconsistent as the vagaries of his god- and rite-creation. There is no basis for the classification of the more important deities except a traditional and ritualistic one, although the minor ones and certain categories of the major are, to a great extent, classified according to their functions or natures. Often a class takes its name from the most important god or gods in it" (Barton, 1946:12).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail on supernatural monitoring.

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "...sometimes the hidit punish the prolongation of a feud, enmity or controversy..." (Barton, 1919:108)

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail.

Food:

– Yes

Notes: "The strongest of all Ifugao taboos is that against eating the food, drinking the water or wine or chewing the betels of an enemy kinship group. It is a powerful deterrent from making peace, for infraction of the taboo entails punishment by a sub-group of the hidit deities with particularly stubborn ailments which no ordinary sickness rites will ameliorate" (Barton, 1946:52).

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: social taboos

Notes: "The Hidit, gods governing relations of enemies, or gods of intergroup propriety, punish the breaking of taboos binding on enemies and their respective groups. In a controversy the litigants and their families are on a basis of theoretical enmity that imposes all the taboos of warfare. Even the unintentional or unknowing infraction of a taboo brings swift punishment from these gods. They seem to have the social function of safeguarding correct procedure. The afflictions they cause are: 'bloating' (often enlarged spleen); coughing, nose bleed, 'quick-coming fatigue,' 'wheezings' and 'short breath'—probably tubercular indications" (Barton, 1930:139).

Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: "...sometimes the hidit punish the prolongation of a feud, enmity or controversy..."

(Barton, 1919:108)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Multiple non-human supernatural beings are described as being the agents of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: "No god is believed to have been the creator and no god is supreme" (Barton, 1930:122).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The strongest of all Ifugao taboos is that against eating the food, drinking the water or wine or chewing the betels of an enemy kinship group. It is a powerful deterrent from making peace, for infraction of the taboo entails punishment by a sub-group of the hidit deities with particularly stubborn ailments which no ordinary sickness rites will ameliorate" (Barton, 1946:52).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: "The hidit (deities) desire peace: but the peace must be made in the proper manner, and accompanied by sacrifice to themselves. The hidit have established the taboo that those who are involved in a controversy or enmity must not chew betels with an adversary, nor be in the same house or gathering or feast with him, nor drink with him, nor receive gifts or hospitality from him. The penalty for breaching this taboo is the affliction by the hidit with diseases of the lungs, throat, voice; the condition known as "big belly," leukaemia, short wind, swelling of the feet, dropsy, etc. This may be said to be the punishment for making peace without ceremonies. But sometimes the hidit punish the prolongation of a feud, enmity or controversy, by afflicting one or

both of the parties as set forth above" (Barton, 1919:108).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

Notes: The only punishment directly described in ethnographic evidence is that of sickness and illness.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

Notes: "The strongest of all Ifugao taboos is that against eating the food, drinking the water or wine or chewing the betels of an enemy kinship group. It is a powerful deterrent from making peace, for infraction of the taboo entails punishment by a sub-group of the hidit deities with particularly stubborn ailments which no ordinary sickness rites will ameliorate" (Barton, 1946:52).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing: there is, consequently, no written law. They have no form of political government: there is, therefore, no constitutional or statutory law. Inasmuch as they have no courts or judges, there is no law based on judicial decisions. Ifugao law has two sources of origin: taboo (which is essentially religious) and custom. The customary law is the more important from the greater frequency of its application" (Barton, 1919:11).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "...the principal crimes, in order of their probable frequency, are: sorcery; adultery; theft; murder (or in the case of women and children, kidnapping); the putting of an innocent person in the position of being considered an accessory to crime; manslaughter; rape of a married woman; arson; incest. Minor crimes are: insult; slander; false accusation; rape of a girl" (Barton, 1919:69).

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: There is clearly a difference between conventional and moral norms, but the difference is not emphasized because punishment for violation of these norms varies and depends on the families involved. See Barton, 1919:63.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of a requirement for celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "The duties of the manikam (the priest who performs these ceremonies) are rather arduous. To say nothing of the ceremonies he conducts, he must fast for a number of days and must observe a number of taboos" (Barton, 1919:79).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The strongest of all Ifugao taboos is that against eating the food, drinking the water or wine or chewing the betels of an enemy kinship group. It is a powerful deterrent from making peace, for infraction of the taboo entails punishment by a sub-group of the hidit deities with particularly stubborn ailments which no ordinary sickness rites will ameliorate" (Barton, 1946:52).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Communal ceremonies (such as the rice ceremonies, see Barton, 1946 page 123), but it does not appear that participation is required.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Ifugao have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, the Ifugao have kin ties, indicating a tribal society. According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10, Descent), the Ifugao have bilateral descent. Additionally, the Ifugao have agamous communities without localized clans or any marked tendency toward either local exogamy or endocamy. Neither patrilineal nor matrilineal kin groups or exogamy are present. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing: there is, consequently, no written law. They have no form of political government: there is, therefore, no constitutional or statutory law. Inasmuch as they have no courts or judges, there is no law based on judicial decisions. Ifugao law has two sources of origin: taboo (which is essentially religious) and custom. The customary law is the more important from the greater frequency of its application" (Barton, 1919:11).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, food storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, food storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxes or tithes.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxes or tithes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing: there is, consequently, no written law. They have no form of political government: there is, therefore, no constitutional or statutory law. Inasmuch as they have no courts or judges, there is no law based on judicial decisions" (Barton, 1919:11).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "Society does not punish injuries to itself except as the censure of public opinion is a punishment. This follows naturally from the fact that there is no organized society. It is only when an injury committed by a person or family falls on another person or family that the injury is punished formally" (Barton, 1919:14).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing: there is, consequently, no written law. They have no form of political government: there is, therefore, no constitutional or statutory law. Inasmuch as they have no courts or judges, there is no law based on judicial decisions. Ifugao law has two sources of origin: taboo (which is essentially religious) and custom. The customary law is the more important from the greater frequency of its application" (Barton, 1919:11).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "The Ifugaos have no form of writing..." (Barton, 1919:11).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Ifugao are intensive agriculturalists with a secondary reliance on hunting. Fishing and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Ifugao are intensive agriculturalists with a secondary reliance on hunting. Fishing and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.